

Towards a Framework for Seismic Data

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Abstract. Over the past decade, Knowledge Graphs (KGs) gained significant attention as a powerful method for knowledge representation. Driven by increasing interest, a paradigm shift has occurred, where the technology of KGs has transitioned from the research domain to the industry and public sector, with companies and organizations increasingly representing their data as Linked Open Data, gaining in that way significant traction for this technology. This paper focuses on KGs in the context of environmental challenges. More specifically, this work concerns KGs that contain seismic event data, such as location, timestamp, magnitude, depth, target date, as well as images before and after the event occurrence. Moreover, a Natural Language Processing (NLP) module is integrated to enhance the KG. That module enables users to query for seismic events in a free-text manner, before addressing them with a relevant response through a dedicated Information Retrieval (IR) component. The KG was constructed with data retrieved from the *Instituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia*, a rich resource that comes with earthquake-related information, such as magnitude, depth, occurrence location, and timestamp. Additionally, public APIs from the *Copernicus Open Access Data Hub* and *ONDA DIAS* are leveraged to provide access to sentinel data, such as images of the event location before and after its occurrence.

Keywords: Knowledge Graph · Information Retrieval · Natural Language Processing · Semantic Framework

1 Introduction

The usage of KGs as a method for representing data has increased significantly in the last five years. The KGs can provide semantically related knowledge, along with interoperability, interlinking, and re-usability of data, that other knowledge bases cannot, while they can also be applied in a variety of domains, such as the representation of knowledge for environmental challenges. For this reason, we can see that more and more industries, as well as the public sector, translate their data into Linked Open Data (LOD).

In this paper, we present a KG for seismic data. In more detail, we present a KG that can represent information for seismic events across the globe. The KG was built

upon the information provided by the Copernicus Data Provider¹ for Sentinels data and the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology² for earthquake data. It also incorporates a NLP mechanism to aid the users address queries in natural language, and retrieve data about a specific event. Moreover, the KG is equipped with a IR mechanism that retrieves semantically related pairs of pre/post images for an event, among other information.

The motivation behind this paper is to present the first KG that contains, to this extent, knowledge about seismic events and sentinel data, for the state of a target location before and after an event. Moreover, the KG presented in this paper can help in providing knowledge about the state of a target environment and the changes that it goes through, while also provide knowledge for possible disaster management scenarios.

The main objective of our study is to introduce the first, to our knowledge, comprehensive and high-quality knowledge resource, specifically dedicated for seismic events. The KG provides valuable insights about the state of a target environment, including pre-event and post-event changes, while also, it offers guidelines for effective disaster management scenarios. Conclusively, our work provides a high-quality RDF representation of seismic events, covering the biggest possible extent of recorded instances.

The main contribution of this study is the quality of data that are introduced in RDF representation, as it represents information about almost all seismic events ever recorded. The plurality of this information occurs because we extract knowledge from the Copernicus Data Provider and the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, which contain information about all the seismic events ever recorded.

The outline of the paper is as follows, we start with related work (Section 2), followed by a presentation of the utilized data and a description of the KG, the NLP module, and the IR mechanism in Section 3. Next, in Section 4 we provide an evaluation of our framework, where we evaluate the consistency and completeness of the KG. Moreover, we compare our framework against a Large Language Model (LLM). We conclude our paper with Section 5, where we summarize the key findings and implications of our study.

2 Related Work

This study delves into three integral components: the KG which represents seismic event data, the NLP mechanism which facilitates user-friendly queries, and the IR mechanism which fetches relevant data from the KG. In this section, we will omit the literature regarding similar NLP components, since the NLP part is mostly a helping component, and we will focus on relevant KG and IR proposals.

Regarding the KG domain, a variety of research attempts have been proposed in the literature that exhibit an adequate resemblance to the target topic of this work. More precisely, one of the most relevant categories may be the KGs for seismic events, while also, the category of KGs regarding the seismic risk domain.

Starting with the former, some indicative approaches may be those of Li & Li (2013), where a KG for semantic representation of textual information is presented with

¹ <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>

² <https://github.com/INGV/openapi>

multi-document summarization, with disaster management being its main aspect, while also the studies of Chou et al. (2010, 2014) may be indicative, where similar KGs were presented. Nevertheless, even though in these works KGs for disaster management may properly be presented, those fall short in representing a specific knowledge for seismic events since they only target information that exists on various disaster management websites, in contrast to the KG proposed in this work.

In a similar sense, regarding the latter category of KGs for the seismic risk domain, an indicative research example may be the work of Murgante et al. (2009). In this work, a promising KG is introduced, which improves semantic interoperability and aims to reduce the economic and social costs associated with seismic events. Nevertheless, the information provided in this work lacks of an extensive depth, in contrast to ours, which encompasses precise details such as location, timestamp, magnitude, and depth of each earthquake.

Continuing with our examination, it would be essential to highlight the IR mechanisms currently utilized in disaster management. To the best of our knowledge, existing IR mechanisms in this domain do not have a direct association with a KG, resulting in a significant oversight of vital semantically related information. For instance, the studies of Islam & Chik (2011); Bouzidi et al. (2019); Shen et al. (2017) can extract data from various websites but lack the reasoning capabilities that a KG can offer. A similar scenario is observed in Pi et al. (2020); Vallejo et al. (2020), where drone footage is analyzed without leveraging a KG. In contrast to such a drawback, our proposed IR mechanism showcases the true potential of a KG, enriching IR and providing an initial direction on how a KG can be used to manage crucial information about a disaster.

Eventually, before concluding our literature overview, a series of research examples regarding the helpfulness of KGs may be useful to be presented. Some example works in that direction are those of Landis et al. (2021), Silva et al. (2013) and Ortmann et al. (2011), where approaches on how a KG could help the preservice of Cultural and Natural heritage in the case of a disaster (such as an earthquake), are presented. Subsequently, the work of Correia et al. (2023) may be an indicative example of how a KG can help a decision support system to access semantically rich data in order to help users take better decisions during a disaster management scenario. The aforementioned research endeavors may serve as supplementary evidence underlining the potential benefits that KGs could confer.

3 Methodology

In this Chapter, we present a description of the data upon which the KG was constructed, along with the KG itself, the NLP mechanism and the IR mechanism.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the architecture, presenting a user interacting with the system through the NLP mechanism, to query the Seismic KG. Subsequently, the IR mechanism retrieves relevant answers and presents them to the user. The Seismic KG acquires data from Copernicus and the Institute of Volcanology, incorporating it into its internal Knowledge Base (KB).

Moreover, it is worth noticing that the NLP mechanism accesses the KG through an endpoint, based on which the KG also plays the role of a client-server application.

Fig. 1: The Architecture of the Seismic Data Framework

Whenever a question is received on the KG endpoint, a SPARQL query is automatically produced, containing all the desired information for the KG.

3.1 Nature of the Data

The data and metadata which are represented in the KG are retrieved from two sources: The Copernicus Data Provider (DHuS and/or ONDA DIAS³) retrieved via the OData/OpenSearch APIs^{4,5}, and the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology for earthquake data, retrieved via the fdsnws-event API. The relevant product type of the Copernicus data for earthquake analysis is the IW SLC for Sentinel-1 Level-1 data. The KG by default will contain the data sources presented below, while also additional data sources related to events or Copernicus data, may also be supported.

- For Sentinel-1 Images:
 - Timestamp (i.e. sensing start)
 - Event ID
 - Image URL
 - Location expressed as polygon or multipolygon
 - Orbit number of the satellite
 - Pass direction of the satellite

- For earthquake metadata:

³ <https://www.onda-dias.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.opensearch.org/>

⁵ <https://www.odata.org/>

- Event identifier
- Coordinates
- Timestamp
- Magnitude and depth of the event

3.2 The Knowledge Graph

In order to cover the different aspects of semantic representation, a domain-specific ontology has been designed to capture metadata referring to sentinel images and events. The ontology extends existing ontologies and standards (i.e. Event Ontology, OWL-Time) to offer the appropriate structures (classes and properties) and represent information related to cities (i.e. city names, coordinates and countries). More specifically, to cover the use case of earthquake identification, sentinel images are related to generic information (i.e. UUID, timestamp, URL), while earthquake events are related to information pertinent to the earthquake (i.e. depth, magnitude, coordinates, timestamp). An example of such a semantic representation is depicted in Figure 2. For each sentinel image, the same ontological schema is applicable for all types of use cases. In case of events, all types of events will contain coordinates and timestamp. Other information might also be included, based on the needs of each use case. The KG is composed of

Fig. 2: The Knowledge Graph for Seismic Data

two main classes **Event** and **Product**. The Event class contains information about the location of the earthquake, such as the country, the city, the coordinates, the timestamp, and the date (i.e., year-date-month). The Product class contains information about the earthquake itself such as the magnitude, the depth, pre/post-seismic photos, a multi

polygon for the area that the image represents, the source from which the photos were extracted, the orbit number and pass direction of the satellite, the product URL, and the unique ID of the product. The distinction in two classes emerges as an intuitive way to segregate data, pertaining to the earthquake event itself, from information related to the geographical location where the earthquake transpired.

3.3 The Natural Language Mechanism

The NLP mechanism was developed so that the KG would support user inquiries, formed as free-text, and it functions in cooperation with the IR module. More precisely, given an input question in free-text form, the NLP mechanism is responsible for identifying various aspects of information that are required for the IR part. In that sense, the NLP mechanism can identify references of Countries (e.g. Greece), Cities (e.g. Athens), Dates (e.g. 3/5/2023), Magnitude numbers (e.g. 6.5), Comparatives (e.g. bigger than), while it can also verify that a target question is referred on an earthquake event.

Starting with the identification of Countries and Cities, three different approaches have been developed to identify such mentions, so that the biggest possible coverage, even for less-populated and famous cities, may be accomplished. Initially, a parsing of the input sentence is performed with the Spacy framework¹ to identify references of geopolitical entities. Then, a second parsing of the input question is performed with the aid of three different geoparsing libraries (namely geonamescache², pycountry³ and geotext⁴). Eventually, a final parsing with a set of manually constructed regular expressions takes place, based on which country and city mentions may be captured through various syntactic and phrase patterns.

Subsequently, the Date identification component leverages both the Spacy framework to identify mentions of dates, while also dedicated regular expressions. A variety of free-text and numeric date formats are being supported through that component (e.g. date formats such as, *01-01-2023*, *1/1*, and *January 1 2023*, among others). Moreover, the Spacy framework and a set of dedicated regular expressions have also been leveraged to identify Magnitude number references both in numeric and in free-text form (e.g. number formats such as, *6.5*, *six point five* or *6 point five*, among others).

In addition, for the identification of Comparative mentions, a variety of different methods, combined in a hybrid approach have been developed. More specifically, various syntactic patterns have been constructed with the aid of regular expressions, while also the Wordnet database Miller (1995) has been utilized to also incorporate a variety of hypernyms and hyponyms, besides straightforward patterns. That component can identify mentions of comparative symbols (e.g. $<$ or $= <$), while also free-text references (e.g. *bigger than*, *bigger or equal than* or *equal to* and various synonyms of those, such as *higher than* or *greater than*, among others)

Eventually, a component to eliminate cases of inputs questions that do not refer to earthquake events has also been developed. For that purpose, a list of earthquake-related

¹ <https://spacy.io/>

² <https://pypi.org/project/geonamescache/>

³ <https://pypi.org/project/pycountry/>

⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/geotext/>

keywords has been manually constructed, based on which the semantic relatedness of each keyword with the sub parts of the input question is examined, to conclude whether the input question refers on earthquake events.

3.4 The Information Retrieval Mechanism

The IR mechanism initially translates the keywords provided from the NLP mechanism (subsection 3.3) from a JSON format into values used by SPARQL queries. The keywords provided are the ones shown below, out of which some are mandatory (M) (i.e., they must exist in order for a SPARQL query to be created), and some optional (O) (i.e., they are not mandatory for a SPARQL query to be formatted).

- **Event:** The type of event (i.e., earthquake (M)).
- **City:** The city of event (M).
- **Country:** The country of event (M).
- **Year:** The year of event (M).
- **Month:** The month of event (O).
- **Day:** The day of event (O).
- **Magnitude:** The magnitude of event (O). (If no magnitude is given then the default value is 5.0).
- **Comparative:** If the requested event is greater or smaller than the value of magnitude (O).
- **Point:** Boolean value that indicates if the location is given in the format of coordinates or city-country pair label (M).
- **Latitude-longitude:** The latitude-longitude of the event (O).

For instance, if the user addresses the question “Give me all the earthquakes that occurred in Montalvo, Ecuador in 2019”, the resulting JSON, after having been parsed by the IR mechanism, will have the following format.

```

Information Retrieval Generated JSON
{
  "page": "1",
  "nlp": {
    "event": "earthquake", "city": "Montalvo",
    "country": "Ecuador", "year": 2019,
    "month": "null", "day": "null",
    "magnitude": "null", "comparative": "null",
  }
}

```

Note that the presence of a solitary result signifies that, during that specific year, only a single earthquake event, surpassing a magnitude of 5.0, had occurred.

Based on this JSON a SPARQL query will be automatically generated in order to retrieve the desired information from the KG. One can see the generated SPARQL query below.

```

        Automatically Generated SPARQL Query
prefix event:<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/event.owl#>
prefix rdf:<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
prefix time:<http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
prefix xsd:<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
SELECT * WHERE {
    ?event rdf:type event:Event.
    OPTIONAL { ?event event:city ?city.}
    OPTIONAL {?event event:country ?country.}
    ?event time:year ?year.
    OPTIONAL {?event time:month ?month.}
    OPTIONAL {?event time:day ?day.}
    OPTIONAL {?event event:place ?place.}
    ?event event:hasSubEvent ?e_event.
    OPTIONAL{?e_event event:hasId ?id.}
    OPTIONAL {?e_event event:magnitude ?magnitude.}
    OPTIONAL {?e_event event:depth ?depth.}
    ?e_event event:latitude ?latitude.
    ?e_event event:longitude ?longitude.
    ?e_event time:inXSDDateTimeStamp ?e_timestamp.
    FILTER (?event=<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm
/event.owl#Event_id>)
}

```

The output returned by the system contains the following information:

- **Magnitude** - The exact magnitude of the earthquake, since the user input might not contain an exact value.
- **Pairs of images** - Pairs of images before and after the event which have the same coordinates and timestamp, with a difference of 12 days (the amount of time needed for the satellite to pass again from the same spot), the orbit number, and the pass direction.
- **Depth** - The depth of the earthquake.
- **Epicenter location** - the exact location of the epicenter of the earthquake.

```

Returned output
{
  "year": "2019",
  "city": "Montalvo",
  "country": "Ecuador",
  "images_before1": {
    "link": "https://colhub.copernicus.eu
/dhus/search?q=uuid:60f5f27c-9ca5
-4834-aa0f-0ab9ccb2249d&format=json",
    "sensing_date": "2019-02-13T23:28:27.036Z",
    "location": "POLYGON ((-78.453781 ...
-1.327742))",
    "orbit_number": "120",
    "pass_direction": "ASCENDING"
  },
  "image_after1": {
    "link": "https://colhub.copernicus.eu
/dhus/search?q=uuid:db2145a3-2a07-4adf
-87c0-e02fbfb1c1a6&format=json",
    "sensing_date": "2019-02-25T23:28:27.035Z",
    "location": "POLYGON ((-78.454636 ...
-1.328015))",
    "orbit_number": "120",
    "pass_direction": "ASCENDING"
  },
  "magnitude": {
    "value": "7.1"
  },
  "depth": {
    "value": "141.4"
  },
  "epicentral_location": {
    "latitude": {
      "value": "-2.13047"
    },
    "longitude": {
      "value": "-76.8867"
    }
  },
  "timestamp": "2019-02-22T10:17:22.50Z"
}

```

Notice that in the output only one pair on images is provided for beautification and space restrictions.

4 Evaluation

To examine the quality of our work, an evaluation of the Seismic KG was conducted on two fronts: completeness and consistency. For completeness assessment, a set of competency questions was formulated to test the KG’s ability to answer based on the information it contains (subsection 4.1). Additionally, the KG’s consistency was evaluated by verifying its adherence to the SHACL constraints (subsection 4.2). Moreover, we conducted a comparative evaluation of the framework’s performance in contrast to the Large Language Model (LLM), ChatGPT⁶. The aforementioned are presented in more details subsequently.

4.1 Completeness of the Knowledge Graph

The completeness of the KG was evaluated through a set of Competency Questions (CQs) assembled during the formation of the official ontology requirements specification document (ORSD) Suárez-Figueroa et al. (2009). For this reason, before constructing the KG, we asked from a number of users to define a set of questions they would like to be answered by the KG. The users were developers and scientists from ESA⁷. In total a number of 48 CQs was collected. In Figure 3 we present an indicative sample of 10 CQs.

- 1) Give me all earthquakes located in the country X and Y with magnitude M.
- 2) Give me all earthquakes located in country X and city Y which occurred in year Z with magnitude M.
- 3) Give me all earthquakes located in country X and city Y which occurred in year Z and month T with magnitude M.
- 4) Give me all earthquakes located in country X and city Y which occurred in year Z, month T, and day D with magnitude M.
- 5) Give me all earthquakes located in the country X with magnitude greater than M.
- 6) Give me all earthquakes located in country X which occurred in year Z with magnitude greater than M.
- 7) Give me all earthquakes located in country X which occurred in year Z and month T with magnitude greater than M.
- 8) Give me all earthquakes located in country X which occurred in year Z, month T, and day D with magnitude greater than M.
- 9) Give me all earthquakes located in the country X and Y with magnitude greater than M.
- 10) Give me all earthquakes located in country X and city Y which occurred in year Z with magnitude greater than M.

Fig. 3: Set of Competency Questions

A series of tests indicated that the completeness of the KG was adequate, since each CQ returned the desired information when translated into a relevant SPARQL

⁶ <https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>

⁷ <https://www.esa.int/>

counterpart. Indicatively, the translation of the second CQ from Figure 3 into a SPARQL counterpart, is shown in subsection 3.4.

4.2 Consistency of the Knowledge Graph

Additionally to the CQs, we performed a validation procedure in order to inspect the syntactic and structural quality of the metadata in the KB, and to examine the consistency of them. Abiding by the closed-world criteria, custom SHACL consistency check rules and native, ontology consistency checks, such as OWL 2 DL reasoning, were utilised. By using the first, one can discover constraint breaches such as cardinality contradictions or imperfect/missing information. By using the later, the semantics at the terminological level, known as TBox, are taken into consideration as a validation measure like in the occasion of class disjointness. An exemplary of shapes constraint that unfolds a constraint is shown below, dictating that all targeted instances of the *Event* class will always have exactly one or less string values in their datatype property *event:country*.

```
event:ev rdf:type sh:NodeShape;
  sh:targetClass event:Event;
  sh:property [
    sh:path event:country;
    sh:datatype xsd:string;
    sh:minInclusive 0;
    sh:maxInclusive 1;
    sh:minCount 1;
    sh:maxCount 1;
  ].
```

4.3 Comparison with Large Language Model

In this subsection we compare how the proposed framework performed against an of-the-self tool for IR on seismic data for disaster management. Since there is no established baseline tool on an extensive event information scale, to compare our framework, we choose to compare its accuracy and quality of information, against the well-known ChatGPT, since the latter stands as a prominent rival in a variety of contemporary contexts.

Concerning the evaluation measures in use, when we refer to *accuracy*, we are evaluating the capacity of the framework and the LLM, to effectively respond to a given question. On the other hand, the *quality of information* pertains to the nature and relevance of the information contained in the answer. In particular, with regard to quality, we assessed whether our framework could furnish information related to the earthquake's epicenter, depth, and location, presented as coordinates or multipolygon data. Additionally, we evaluated whether the framework could supply links to pertinent images associated with a target earthquake in question. Similarly for the LLM.

We tested both tools in a set of 600 questions, out of which our framework could answer 480, and the LLM could answer 200. One can check the accuracy of both tools

in Table 1. All the evaluation questions were retrieved from the aforementioned CQ templates.

Seismic Framework	80%
ChatGPT	33.3%

Table 1: Accuracy of the framework and the LLM.

Conclusively, of utmost significance for our evaluation was to discern the nature of information that ChatGPT would present on its responses and compare that with the information our framework can deliver. It appeared that ChatGPT could solely furnish information on the earthquake’s depth and magnitude across the limited 200 questions it could address. On the contrary, and as it was already mentioned, our framework can deliver an extensive array of essential details, such as the earthquake’s epicenter, depth, precise timestamp, multipolygon representation of the location, and pre/post-images containing vital information about the image’s orbit number, pass direction, sensing timestamp, and multipolygon data.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented a KG specifically designed for the seismic domain which enables the representation of seismic events worldwide. The KG incorporates a NLP mechanism to facilitate the user experience, which allows users to pose queries in free-text for data retrieval. Additionally, the KG incorporates an IR mechanism, capable of retrieving semantically related pairs of pre/post images for a target seismic event, among other relevant information.

The key innovation of this study lies in the high-quality RDF representation of the data, which encompasses information about all ever-recorded seismic events. This breadth of information is made possible by extracting knowledge from the comprehensive datasets, that are provided by the Copernicus Data Provider and the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology.

To evaluate the current state of our work, a two fold goal was set. On the one hand, the completeness and the consistency of the KG were evaluated, while on the other hand the quantity and quality of the responses retrieved by the target framework against those of a famous LLM, were compared. The completeness of the KG (subsection 4.1) was evaluated with a series of CQs, which were collected by domain experts. More specifically, each CQ was converted into a SPARQL query and examined whether each one of them could return appropriate results. All the evaluated CQs returned appropriate results, indicating in that way that the proposed KG is capable of providing essential information in a disaster management scenario. Moreover, the consistency of the KG (subsection 4.2) was evaluated with a set of 21 SHACL validation expressions (shapes), where none of them returned any invalidation of the rule. Eventually, a validation to

identify whether instances that belong to an intersection of classes, had also been applied. No such intersection exists in the KG, which indicates that the KG does not carry any noise or any sort of conflicting information.

Regarding the evaluation against other baseline methods (in our case ChatGPT), our initial expectation was indeed for our framework to outperform ChatGPT in terms of accuracy. This anticipation was based on our framework's access to a diverse set of knowledge bases containing domain-specific information on earthquakes and satellite data (e.g. Onda-Dias⁸, Colhub⁹, ColHub2¹⁰, ColHub3¹¹, SciHub¹², and ApiHub¹³). However, the extent that our framework outperformed ChatGPT was a quite unexpected, though pleasant outcome. To elaborate further, the only questions that our proposed framework could not answer, were those that contained a combination of city-country pairs which was not valid or did not exist. Additionally, there were some cases where the framework couldn't response due to a misspelled city or country name.

Looking ahead, our future objectives would be to align the framework presented in this paper with other disaster management frameworks that utilize KGs as their underlying knowledge representation. Achieving such an alignment, would make a possible extension of our KG with information obtained from another KG, to enhance the overall knowledge pool (e.g. the XR4DRAMA disaster management KG Vassiliades et al. (2023), or add information in the existing KG from other vocabularies such as the Management of Crisis vocabulary Shih et al. (2013). Furthermore, we aim to extend the representation of information to encompass other catastrophic natural events beyond earthquakes, broadening in that way the scope and the utility of the KG.

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⁸ <https://www.onda-dias.eu/cms/>

⁹ <https://colhub.copernicus.eu/dhus/>

¹⁰ <https://colhub2.copernicus.eu/dhus/>

¹¹ <https://colhub3.copernicus.eu/dhus/>

¹² <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>

¹³ <https://apihub.copernicus.eu/>

References

- Bouzidi, Z., Amad, M., & Boudries, A. (2019). Intelligent and real-time alert model for disaster management based on information retrieval from multiple sources. *International Journal of Advanced Media and Communication*, 7(4), 309–330.
- Chou, C.-H., Zahedi, F. M., & Zhao, H. (2010). Ontology for developing web sites for natural disaster management: methodology and implementation. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics-Part A: Systems and Humans*, 41(1), 50–62.
- Chou, C.-H., Zahedi, F. M., & Zhao, H. (2014). Ontology-based evaluation of natural disaster management websites. *Mis Quarterly*, 38(4), 997–1016.
- Correia, A., Água, P. B., & Simões-Marques, M. (2023). The role of ontologies and linked open data in support of disaster management. In *Disaster management and information technology: Professional response and recovery management in the age of disasters* (pp. 393–407). Springer.
- Islam, S. T., & Chik, Z. (2011). Disaster in bangladesh and management with advanced information system. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 20(5), 521–530.
- Landis, C., Wiseman, C., Smith, A. F., & Stephens, M. (2021). Ganch: Using linked open data for georgia’s natural, cultural and historic organizations’ disaster response. *Code4Lib Journal*(50).
- Li, L., & Li, T. (2013). An empirical study of ontology-based multi-document summarization in disaster management. *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics: systems*, 44(2), 162–171.
- Miller, G. A. (1995). Wordnet: a lexical database for english. *Communications of the ACM*, 38(11), 39–41.
- Murgante, B., Scardaccione, G., & Casas, G. (2009). Building ontologies for disaster management: seismic risk domain. In *Urban and regional data management* (pp. 271–280). CRC Press.
- Ortmann, J., Limbu, M., Wang, D., & Kauppinen, T. (2011). Crowdsourcing linked open data for disaster management. In *Proceedings of the terra cognita workshop on foundations, technologies and applications of the geospatial web in conjunction with the iswc* (pp. 11–22).
- Pi, Y., Nath, N. D., & Behzadan, A. H. (2020). Disaster impact information retrieval using deep learning object detection in crowdsourced drone footage. In *Eg-ice 2020 workshop on intelligent computing in engineering, proceedings* (pp. 134–143).
- Shen, S., Murzintcev, N., Song, C., & Cheng, C. (2017). Information retrieval of a disaster event from cross-platform social media. *Information Discovery and Delivery*.
- Shih, F., Seneviratne, O., Liccardi, I., Patton, E., Meier, P., & Castillo, C. (2013). Democratizing mobile app development for disaster management. In *Joint proceedings of the workshop on ai problems and approaches for intelligent environments and workshop on semantic cities* (pp. 39–42).
- Silva, T., Wuwongse, V., & Sharma, H. N. (2013). Disaster mitigation and preparedness using linked open data. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 4, 591–602.

- Suárez-Figueroa, M. C., Gómez-Pérez, A., & Villazón-Terrazas, B. (2009). How to write and use the ontology requirements specification document. In *Otm confederated international conferences" on the move to meaningful internet systems"* (pp. 966–982).
- Vallejo, D., Castro-Schez, J. J., Glez-Morcillo, C., & Albusac, J. (2020). Multi-agent architecture for information retrieval and intelligent monitoring by uavs in known environments affected by catastrophes. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 87, 103243.
- Vassiliades, A., Symeonidis, S., Diplaris, S., Tzanetis, G., Vrochidis, S., Bassiliades, N., & Kompatsiaris, I. (2023). Xr4drama knowledge graph: A knowledge graph for disaster management. In *2023 IEEE 17th International Conference on Semantic Computing (ICSC)* (pp. 262–265).